

Stig2Health: Stigma-directed services to improve ‘linkage to care’ for people living with HIV in rural Tanzania: study protocol for a nested pre-post implementation study within the Kilombero and Ulanga Antiretroviral Cohort

Table S2: Overview lay counselor competency list

Competency	Knowledge	Skills
Effective communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can describe basic communication skills needed to conduct and lead group therapy/education, mobile health, and lay counselling. • Knows about verbal and non-verbal communication. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active listening skills. • Explanation of concepts in a simple manner. • Non-verbal communication, such as maintain eye contact, expressing empathy. • Focus on resources, use strength-based, unconditional, and non-judgmental communication.
Delivery of group support therapy following SOPs/Checklist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understands the principles of group dynamics. • Knowledgeable on topics they must deliver and know their own limits, so that they can consult professionals when faced with questions or situations they cannot address or solve themselves. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lead and conduct group therapy sessions with confidence and in an interactive and friendly manner. • Engage with empathy, so patients share their experiences with each other. • Take time to explain new concepts to participants so they can follow (e.g., mood barometer, sharing feelings).
Self-awareness and social consciousness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aware of their HIV status and are open to sharing their HIV status for the sake of advising and helping other client who are struggling with their (new) diagnosis. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide unbiased first-hand information on coping with living with HIV through their own experience while considering the client’s feelings, worries and follow confidentiality.
Provide basic counselling to newly diagnosed HIV patients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledgeable on basic HIV/AIDS topics (disease and prevention), such as HIV staging, ART adherence, side effects and storage of ART, prevention/PrEP/PEP, disclosure, sexual transmitted diseases, and coping skills. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interact with new HIV individuals offering counselling and shares accurate, unbiased basic education on HIV.
Conduct questionnaires using ODK toolkit, Basic IT skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the basis of the different questionnaires used (PHQ9, adapted Berger and other questionnaires). • IT skills for data collection. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Able to conduct the questionnaires clearly and capturing the right information. • Offer unbiased clarifications when needed. • Use of tablet, taking pictures, use of the open data kit tool to collect study data.